

First report on Communities of Practice

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ABSTRACT

The report presents the work done to plan, establish, manage, and monitor Communities of Practice (CoP) in WIDER UPTAKE. Communities of practice is an approach to establish and facilitate social learning and co-development towards a common objective. The overall objective in WIDER UPTAKE is the upscaling of water smart solutions. The work on CoPs has thus far centred on the demonstration cases, where *local CoPs* –have been established to facilitate collaboration and engage relevant stakeholders. Despite Covid-19, all CoPs are active and progressing towards their stated aims. The set-up and type of stakeholders involved varies, depending on the solutions and challenges in focus. At the *project CoP* level, virtual workshops on cross-cutting topics (so far phosphorus removal and water reuse) and a forum for "Young Professionals" have been initiated, but face-to-face interaction and further efforts from the PMT are needed. At the *trans-project CoP* level, a collaboration has been established with the other projects funded under the call "Water in the Context of the Circular Economy". While this is crucial to enable wider uptake of the project solutions, other relevant communities, both within and beyond the EU, will also be addressed in the coming phase. Furthermore, it is important to extend the dialogue, to include experience-sharing across cases and research groups working on related topics.

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Learning, co-development, stakeholders, Communities of Practice

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	8
1 INTRODUCTION.....	9
2 THE CONCEPT COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE.....	9
3 COPS FOR INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS	11
4 SOCIAL LEARNING IN COPS	13
5 COPS AND CULTURAL DIFFERENCES.....	15
6 COP APPROACH IN WIDER UPTAKE	17
6.1 A process on multiple levels.....	17
6.2 Local CoPs.....	17
6.3 Project CoP process	19
6.4 Trans-Project CoP activities	20
7 COP MANAGEMENT AND SUPPORT	20
7.1 CoPs as a joint responsibility	20
7.2 Planning and launching of Local CoPs	21
7.3 Management and support of Local CoPs.....	23
7.4 Management of project and trans-project CoP activity	24
7.5 Overview of resources and infrastructure.....	25
8 COP MONITORING	26
9 COP ACTIVITY UP TO M18	29
9.1 Local CoP, Sicily	29

9.2	Local CoP, Hamar	32
9.3	Local CoP, Stavanger	36
9.4	Local CoP, Ghana	39
9.5	Local CoP, Prague	42
9.6	Local CoP, Netherlands	46
9.7	Project CoP activities.....	48
9.8	Trans-project CoP activities.....	50
10	LESSONS LEARNED AND WAY FORWARD	51
11	CONCLUSION	52
12	REFERENCES	52
	ANNEX 1: 2-PAGER ON COPS IN WIDER UPTAKE	55
	ANNEX 2: EVALUATION FORM, LOCAL COP WORKSHOPS.....	57

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Visualisation of the difference between teams, CoPs, and wider networks. ..	10
Figure 2: CoP levels of participations (based on Wenger et al. 2002).....	14
Figure 3: Country scores on cultural dimensions (*based on www.hofstede-insights.com/).	16
Figure 4: Three-level approach to CoPs in WIDER UPTAKE.	17
Figure 5: Schematic illustration of Local CoP process.....	19
Figure 6: Giorgio Mannina presenting at Local CoP webinar in Sicily 15th June 2021. Photo: Alida Cosenza.....	30
Figure 7: Tour of facilities at the initial Local CoP workshop in Hamar. Left: Senior Staff at HIAS, in front of pilot struvite unit. Right: Director Grethe Olsbye and colleague in front of soil products. Photos: Sigrid Damman.....	33
Figure 8: Participants at Local CoP workshop 6th October 2020, in front of one of IVAR's WWTPs. Photo: Sigrid Damman.....	37
Figure 9: Participants at the first Local CoP workshop in Ghana, including coordinator Herman Helness on the screen to the right. Photos: Gordon Akon-Yamga.	40
Figure 10: Prof. Wanner presenting in Prague, 29. June 2021. Photo: Iveta Ruzickova.	44

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Key topics and questions for planning and launching CoPs (Koti et al. 2017)...	22
Table 2: Local CoPs, core groups and roles.....	23
Table 3: Resources and infrastructure provided for the CoP activities.	26
Table 4: Criteria and indicators for evaluation and monitoring of the Local CoPs.....	28
Table 5: Participation at first Local CoP workshop in Palermo.	29
Table 6: Summary evaluation by facilitating research partner, Local CoP in Sicily.	31
Table 7: Participation at first Local CoP workshop in Hamar.....	32
Table 8: Summary evaluation of Local CoP in Hamar at Month 18, by facilitating research partner.	35
Table 9: Distribution of participants at the initial Local CoP workshop in Stavanger... 	36
Table 10: Summary evaluation of Local CoP activity in Stavanger by month 18, provided by facilitating research partner.	38
Table 11: Participants at Local CoP launching workshop in Accra, October 2020.....	39
Table 12: Summary evaluation of Local CoP activity in Ghana, by the facilitating research partner.	41
Table 13: Distribution of participants, Local CoP workshop in Prague 29th June 2021. 	43
Table 14: Summary evaluation of Local CoP activity in Prague, by facilitating research partner, month 18.	45
Table 15: Participants at the initial (virtual) workshop for the Local CoP in the Netherlands.	46
Table 16: Summary evaluation of Local CoP activity in the Netherlands by month 18, provided by the facilitating research partner.	48

List of Abbreviations

AMAP: Water utility, WIDER UPTAKE partner (Sicily)

ANCI: National Association Italian Municipalities

ATI: Water Territorial Assemblies (Italy)

Bio-P: biological phosphorous removal

B-WaterSmart: H2020 project, Promoting water-smart economies and societies in coastal Europe.

CE: Circular Economy

CoP: Community of Practice

CSIR: Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (Ghana)

CTU: Czech Technical University

DoA: Description of Action

EASME: Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (EU)

GOCIWA: Governance Assessment for Circular Economy based on Water Resources

HIAS: Water utility, WIDER UPTAKE partner (Norway)

IS: Industrial Symbiosis

IVAR: Water utility, WIDER UPTAKE partner (Norway)

KWR: KWR Water Research Institute (Netherlands)

MoU: Memorandum of Understanding

NEXTGEN: H2020 project, Towards a next generation of water systems and services for the circular economy.

NPSP: Producer of biocomposite materials (Netherlands)

NTNU: Norwegian University of Science and Technology

OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

PMT: Project Management Team

PVS: Water utility, WIDER UPTAKE partner (Czech Republic)

REA: Research Executive Agency (EU)

REWAISE: H2020 project; REsilient WAtEr Innovation for Smart Economy

SOVAK: Water Utility Association of the Czech Republic

SSGL: Sewerage Systems Ghana Ltd

STOP-IT: H2020 project; Strategic, Tactical, Operational Protection of water Infrastructure against cyber-physical Threats

UCT: University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague

ULTIMATE: H2020 project; H2020 project; indUstry water-utiLiTy symbiosis for a sMarter wAtEr society

UNIPA: University of Palermo

UWWTD: Urban WasteWater Treatment Directive

VLSC: Virtual Learning and Sharing Centre

WATERSHARE: international network of water utilities, research organisations and solution providers committed to sharing knowledge, expertise, and resources (coordinated by KWR)

WATERMINING: Next generation water-smart management systems: large scale demonstrations for a circular economy and society

WP: Work Package

WWTP: WasteWater Treatment Plant

Executive summary

WIDER UPTAKE aims to implement and upscale circular water solutions enabling industrial symbiosis (IS). Previous research has shown that collaboration and partnership are conducive factors for achieving IS. Therefore, the project applies Communities of Practice (CoP), as a social learning concept. The underlying idea is that co-development involving practitioners and researchers from different disciplines, as well as different categories of external stakeholders, is needed to overcome present barriers and promote circular economy based on water resources.

Three levels of Communities of Practice (local, project, and trans-project) have been established. *Local CoPs*, centred on the project demonstration cases in Norway, the Netherlands, Ghana, Sicily, and Czech Republic, form the basis, where project partners engage with stakeholders that are essential for implementing and upscaling the demonstrated solutions. The format and type of stakeholders involved varies across the five cultural contexts and are tailored to meet the key challenges addressed in each case. Where current regulations or regulatory gaps are defined as a main focus (in Italy and the Czech Republic), the Local CoPs have engaged high level stakeholders such as regional authorities and politicians, to the extent allowed during Covid-19. In the cases where e.g., social acceptance, market development, and technical issues are more in focus (in Ghana, the Netherlands and Norway), a bottom-up approach has been taken. Potential collaboration partners, customers and end-users have so far been the predominant types of stakeholders.

Beyond the local CoPs, the *Project CoP* aims to connect project partners and others across cases and project work packages, and activities at the *Trans-project CoP* level are to ensure interaction with e.g., other projects on circular economy based on water resources and other relevant communities in the EU and beyond.

Thus far, the CoP work in WIDER UPTAKE has been centred on the local CoPs. Initial launching workshops have been conducted, some in a physical format and others in a digital format due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The activity within the different CoPs varies. Most CoPs have frequent meetings with its core members (utilities and industrial/research partner), and some have conducted follow-up workshops with a wider set of stakeholders. At Project CoP level, the partners have not had the chance to meet physically, due to Covid-19. However, a series of web workshops has been established, on topics of common interest. A forum for exchange and co-learning between PhD candidates and other young researchers has also been put in place. In terms of the trans-project CoP, collaboration with the other projects financed under the Horizon 2020 call on "Building a water-smart economy and society" call has been established.

Despite the impacts of Covid-19, the work on Communities of Practice in WIDER UPTAKE is well under way. To further increase collaboration and co-learning, there is the need for more face-to-face interaction, both between the partners and with stakeholders external to the project. Going forward, a series of monthly lunch webinars will be arranged. If the pandemic subsides as expected, "mobile labs" will also be realised, starting from 2022. Considering the Trans-project CoP activity, the collaboration with the "sister projects" under the same call will become even more important in the coming phase, when further stakeholder dialogue is needed to validate, disseminate, and implement results. In addition, other relevant communities, both within and beyond the EU, must also be addressed.

1 Introduction

WIDER UPTAKE aims to demonstrate and implement water-smart solutions. With demonstration activities in five different countries, the project brings together water utilities and other industry actors in order to promote industrial symbiosis, based on water reuse and resource recovery, of nutrients, energy, and materials for innovative biocomposite production.

Previous research suggests that to transition to a circular economy and ensure investments in appropriate and effective technologies, active involvement from a broad set of stakeholders and strong levels of collaboration is key (Ghisellini et al., 2016). WIDER UPTAKE therefore applies the concept of Communities of Practice (CoPs) to facilitate learning and co-development, as well as broader stakeholder dialogue, both at the level of the individual demo case, at project level, and in relation to other communities engaged in circular economy based on water resources. CoPs provide forums where water utilities, industry actors, academics and other relevant public or private stakeholders can:

- learn from each other;
- discuss implications of the technical demo case results and research findings; and
- develop possible solutions to how existing barriers can be overcome and the technological solutions implemented.

The CoP concept emphasizes the need to build inter-personal relations, trust and understanding over time, in order to bridge boundaries and share explicit as well as more tacit forms of knowledge. A social learning approach may expand participants' perspectives and provide a basis for innovation and best practice development.

CoPs are increasingly applied in the water sector (e.g., in European initiatives such as WATERSHARE, STOP-IT and NEXTGEN). This document provides background and outlines the approach taken in WIDER UPTAKE. It is inspired by and builds upon work done in the H2020 project STOP-IT (Koti et al. 2017), which also is taken further in some of our 'sister projects, i.e., other H2020 projects funded in the call H2020-SC5-2019-2, CE-SC5-04-2019 — Building a water-smart economy and society, e.g., B-WaterSmart and Ultimate.

2 The concept Communities of Practice

Communities of Practice (CoP) was initially developed as a theoretical approach to understanding the nature of learning and knowledge in smaller groups within an organization. Wenger and Snyder (2000) define CoPs as '*groups of people informally bound together by expertise and passion for a joint enterprise*'. That is, they see CoPs as different from regular project or work teams, in that they are less defined by specific tasks and deliverables, and more diverse and fluid in terms of objectives, outputs and membership, but kept together by a desire to learn and build new knowledge in a specific enterprise or topic area.

Figure 1: Visualisation of the difference between teams, CoPs, and wider networks.

As illustrated above (Figure 1), CoPs thus tend to be less structured than teams, but more formal than networks, and also less goal oriented than ordinary project teams, but to have more in common than external networks, which tend to be opportunity-driven and characterized by weaker ties.

An important condition for CoPs to work is that the members interact on a regular basis (Wenger et al., 2002) and share their knowledge, experience and expertise within a particular field. Examples of CoPs can be engineers working on deep-sea drilling, frontline manufacturing operations managers discussing new production technologies, or gang members learning how to survive on the street.

Three constitutive dimensions set Communities of Practice apart from e.g., a neighbourhood, which is also considered as a community. These dimensions are *domain*, *community* and *practice* (Wenger-Trayner and Wenger-Trayner, 2015):

- **Domain:** A CoP is defined by a shared domain of interest. Membership involves a commitment to the domain and shared competence. An example may be medical doctors, psychologists, nutritionists, and others working to help patients and develop a better approach for treating anorexia.
- **Community:** Based on the shared interest in the domain, CoP members develop and share information, help each other with problem-solving, and engage in discussions. Members do not necessarily work together on a daily basis but build relationships that enable co-learning. These relationships can be face-to-face but also virtual.
- **Practice:** CoP members do not only share a common interest but develop a common practice and a repertoire of resources. These resources can take the form of experiences, stories, tools, or ways of addressing recurring problems. The development of a shared practice takes time and presupposes continuous interaction.

To enhance a CoP, it is crucial that the three dimensions are developed in parallel (Wenger-Trayner & Wenger-Trayner, 2015). Previous research shows that this is easier for intradisciplinary than transdisciplinary fields (Hearn and White, 2009). Linking knowledge, policy, and practice, and as in WIDER UPTAKE, also participants from different countries and continents, adds complexity. Beyond enhancing pre-existing knowledge and practices, societal challenges frame the work, and appropriateness and acceptability of the output and solutions are key issues.

Fulgenzi et al (2020) discuss some of the challenges that often are encountered in co-production across disciplines:

- a) Stakeholders may have competing interests and strategies, framing of policy issues, and knowledge bases, which may be difficult to align;
- b) Participatory initiatives entail additional time/costs for facilitation and community management, and require trust from partners, that this investment will not be wasted; and
- c) There may be power asymmetries; differences in issue framings, capacity to participate, and understanding of the knowledge to be developed can affect the relevance, legitimacy, and quality of the joint knowledge work

These challenges underscore the need to work actively to facilitate social learning and community building in an ambitious research and innovation project.

3 CoPs for Industrial Symbiosis

Industrial Symbiosis (IS) has been defined as a *"collaborative environmental action whereby firms share or exchange by-products, materials, energy, or waste as a way to economically reduce aggregated environmental impacts"* (Walls and Paquin, 2015, p.32), with emphasis on the environmental objective. However, there are also definitions that place more weight on the economic aspect. Baldassarre et al. (2019, p. 446) simply define IS as *'a collective approach to competitive advantage in which separate industries exchange materials, energy, water and/or by products'*. The objective is thus to use waste streams to generate value, bringing life to the idiom *one man's trash is another man's treasure*.

In order to achieve IS, relation-building between actors and broader stakeholder interaction is essential (Vanhamäki et al., 2020). In relation to the demonstration cases in WIDER UPTAKE, the development of local Communities of Practice is thus of key importance, as they are set up to facilitate interaction and communication between the key partners (water companies/utilities and technology providers) and stakeholders that are relevant for the upscaling of the solutions being tested.

From a circular economy perspective, IS can be understood as an archetypical business model that depends on industrial actors 'sharing infrastructure and by-products to improve resource efficiency and to create value from waste' (Baldassarre et al., 2019, p. 449). IS has also been put on the political agenda, as an element in the Roadmap for a Resource Efficient Europe (COM(2011) 571), and regarded as a systemic innovation element vital for future green growth by the OECD (OECD, 2021).

IS benefits from geographical proximity as it facilitates easier interaction between the actors within the network (Bocken et al., 2016). In addition, cognitive and organizational dimensions are key elements in interactive learning and innovation within industrial networks (Boschma, 2005). On this background, modern IS practice emphasizes cooperation through transactions involving information and knowledge sharing, as well as material resources. According to Lombardi and Laybourn (2012:); *'IS engages diverse organizations in a network to foster eco-innovation and long-term culture change. Creating and sharing knowledge through the network yields mutually profitable transactions for novel sourcing of required inputs, value-added destinations for non-product outputs, and improved business and technical processes'*. Other studies further emphasize that orchestrating IS relationships and transactions among companies is a complex and dynamic process (Boons et al. 2016; Paquin & Howard-Grenville 2012)

Yeo et al (2019), based on a broad literature review, identify six steps in IS creation:

1. Preliminary assessment (develop better understanding of needs and requirements, local conditions, and suitability);
2. Engage businesses (create awareness, interest, identify and recruit members, foster collaborative culture);
3. Find synergy opportunities (information sharing, input/output analysis, identify synergies);
4. Determine feasibility (consideration of cost/benefits, risks);
5. Implement transactions (establish transactions, assess their impacts); and
6. Documentation (capture success cases).

For all these steps, there is the need for a joint forum. Moreover, the progression from step to step requires knowledge production at the interface between different enterprises and practices. It also depends on the ability to build increasing levels of trust between the actors, enough to make it worthwhile for them to invest time and share relevant information. In many cases, such as in WIDER UPTAKE, the process also requires interaction across sectors, characterized by different norms and perspectives.

The CoP concept may be particularly useful in this context. Beyond technical work meetings, it can help generate a shared vision/agenda of Industrial Symbiosis at the demo case level. Moreover, working through CoPs may engage user partners and researchers from different disciplines, as well as wider stakeholders, in a joint process, focused on the practical opportunities and challenges associated with circular water solutions. Interaction, learning and knowledge development between the different stakeholders in the CoP may, in turn, lead to other, unforeseen potentials for IS in the user cases.

This may also be fruitful in a sustainability transition perspective, where demonstrations and projects such as WIDER UPTAKE may be seen as "experiments" or first steps towards a wider system change. In the sustainability transitions literature, three steering notions for such experiments have been distinguished, namely deepening, broadening, and scaling up (Van den Bosch et al. 2008).

Deepening – striving to learn as much as possible from a transition experiment in a specific context. Especially higher order, or reflexive learning that may change existing frames of reference. Guiding principles are to take in account uncertainties, create space for

intermediate adaptations, formulate learning objectives in advance and build upon learning experiences from other experiments.

Broadening – implying that experiments that are successful in a certain context are repeated ‘smartly’ in different contexts, by incorporating lessons learned and continuously adapting to the new context. Guiding principles are to set up experiments with high potential to be repeated in a broader context, use a sustainability vision, organise feedback loops between the experiments (e.g., demo cases in WIDER UPTAKE) and the wider transition pathways and visions to be developed.

Scaling up – activities aimed at embedding the experiment in the structure, culture, and practices at a higher scale level for a wider impact. Guiding principles for scaling up are stimulating institutional embedding, gaining structural support, and involving key players from the regime, overcoming (institutional) barriers, and making the experiment part of a broader process of change.

4 Social learning in CoPs

According to Wenger et. al. (2002), learning processes can be cultivated and stimulated by bringing people with different background and prior knowledge together to develop new insight into a common topic area. The concept builds on seven principles:

- 1. Design for evolution** – Communities tend to be organic and dynamic. CoPs are therefore best built on existing networks, beyond any particular design. The main purpose when designing CoPs is to catalyse an evolutionary dynamic on this basis.
- 2. Open a dialogue between inside and outside perspectives** – Good CoP design depends on developing internal knowledge, but also on bringing in outside perspectives, which may provide new information and challenge pre-existing understandings, helping the community identify and recognize potential opportunities.
- 3. Invite different levels of participation** – Community participation is often divided into three levels of participation, as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: CoP levels of participations (based on Wenger et al. 2002).

The *core group* participates actively in the core activities of the CoP and often takes the responsibility and leadership to set the direction for goals and targets. The second level is the *active group*, which includes more members and meets regularly, but not as often as the core group. The third level encompasses the *peripheral group*, of participants who only rarely attend, but are rather passive spectators. In some cases, they may have less interest in the domain, in other cases they may be novices, who are yet to become acquainted with the tasks, vocabulary, and organizing principles of the community. As interests are changing as communities evolve, levels of participation are a dynamic part of CoPs.

4. **Develop both public and private community spaces** – CoPs may include both public spaces, such as a community website or public meetings, and processes and arenas where the focus is more on the relationship among community members. As progress mainly is based on the latter, core members and the community coordinator should facilitate internal information sharing, relation-building and co-learning.
5. **Focus on value** – Focus on value for its members is what drives a CoP forward. The full value of a community may not be apparent in the beginning. Many CoPs initially focus on problems and needs, but activities and relationships are a source to discover new opportunities and results. While the value may be hard to specify, keeping it in focus throughout the time is important for the real impact of a community.
6. **Combine familiarity and excitement** – Creating a familiar environment will help members feel comfortable and promote sharing. At the same time, novelty is promoted through divergent thinking. Thus, CoPs should combine familiarity and excitement.
7. **Create a rhythm for the community** – Regular meetings, interactions and activities create continuity in a community. Establishing milestones will help CoPs to find their rhythm, which is important to keep the community alive at different stages. A balance between activities with the different levels of participation is key.

In addition, Vincent et al (2018) highlight three characteristics that are especially important for the success of transdisciplinary COPs:

Bringing together researchers and users from the start of the project. The earlier in the decision-making process relationships are established, the more effective it is likely to be (Hanger et al. 2013).

Ensuring openness and empathy for each other's contexts. The most effective teams are found where all parties are open to the notion of collaboration, and willing to put themselves in the position of other disciplinary backgrounds/job roles in order to understand the contexts of decisions.

Regular face-to-face communication, where possible. Continuous and patient communication is needed, particularly at the beginning of a project, in order to share differing viewpoints. Face-to-face interaction is especially important for awareness raising of the specificities of the contexts of scientists and users, for example social constraints, uncertainties in model outputs, as well as the decision-making process and how inputs can be tailored to better inform this.

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the social principles for CoPs have been challenged in WIDER UPTAKE, where most of the interaction so far has been digital and many of the partner institutions and individuals did not know each other before. The basic principles are understood and embraced, but some of the immediate rewards and benefits, e.g., in terms of informal information exchange, personal relation-building and in-depth discussions, have been more difficult to achieve. Considering the focus on IS, ensuring empathy and openness for different contexts and perspectives is important. With a view to the noted challenges, maintaining the focus on value is critical.

5 CoPs and cultural differences

While the need to establish an internal culture of collaboration and trust is emphasized in the literature on CoPs, there has been less discussion of the link between CoPs and their wider cultural context. In WIDER UPTAKE, a basic tenet is that CoPs must be tailored to the cultural context they operate in. A format that works well in Norway, may not be the best in Sicily or Ghana, and materials and facilitation methods appreciated in the Czech Republic may not be as well received in the Netherlands, and so on.

This can be related to previous research on differences in national and organizational cultures, such as those presented by Hofstede et al. (2010). Based on broad, international comparisons, Hofstede and colleagues identified six different dimensions which vary significantly, and in turn have implications for management, organization and what may be desired or appropriate forms of work and business interaction. It must be emphasized that these findings pertain to patterns at aggregate level, which should not be confused with value differences at the individual level (Hofstede 2011).

Put briefly, the six dimensions can be described as follows:

- **Power Distance** - the extent to which the less powerful members of organizations and institutions accept and expect that power is distributed unequally
- **Uncertainty Avoidance** – a society's tolerance for ambiguity, the extent to which members are prone to feel either uncomfortable or comfortable in unstructured situations.
- **Individualism** - versus Collectivism, referring to the degree to which people are integrated into groups. I-consciousness and personal opinion, versus we-consciousness and emphasis on harmony.
- **Masculinity** – versus Femininity, finding that in 'feminine' countries, both men and women share the same modest, caring values, whereas in 'masculine' countries they are more assertive and competitive, but with a larger gap between men's and women's values.
- **Long-term** – versus Short-term orientation, the extent to which the future is in focus, as opposed to here and now.
- **Indulgence** – versus Restraint, allowing relatively free gratification of basic and natural human desires related to enjoying life, versus control, regulation by means of strict social norms.

The countries where WIDER UPTAKE's demo cases and Local CoPs are located score differently on these dimensions, as shown below (Figure 3):

Figure 3: Country scores on cultural dimensions (*based on www.hofstede-insights.com/).

Hofstede's model is debated, and the specific scores need not concern us here, but the level of variation is significant, and may have implications for how CoPs best may be organised in the different settings.

6 CoP approach in WIDER UPTAKE

6.1 A process on multiple levels

Inspired by previous collaboration in the STOP-IT project (Koti et al. 2017), WIDER UPTAKE has decided to work with three different, yet interrelated levels of Communities of Practice, respectively termed Local, Project and Trans-project CoPs (see Figure 4).

The aim with this multi-level approach (described in detail in sections 6.2–6.4) is to ensure knowledge generation and co-creation both within and across the project demonstration cases, and with other relevant communities, especially the other projects funded by Horizon2020 in the framework of the EU-programme “Water in the Context of the Circular Economy”.

The CoPs are seen as a kind of ‘glue’ in the project, that shall strengthen relations and support collaboration and co-development in the demonstration cases and work packages, and enable cross-learning, through a number of dedicated CoP activities on topics of common interest.

Figure 4: Three-level approach to CoPs in WIDER UPTAKE.

The focus will be on interdisciplinary learning and knowledge development that is **relevant for practice**. Thus, as illustrated in Figure 4, the basis of this work is the activities in Local CoPs, where the local partners and key stakeholders related to the respective demonstration cases interact. The following sections describe how the three levels of activities are defined and have developed in WIDER UPTAKE.

6.2 Local CoPs

The local CoPs have a stable core that interacts regularly, in order to develop a community in a real sense. The type and number of core members, and exactly how often and how

these stakeholders interact will vary from case to case, depending on their specific objectives and local context (as well as limitations due to Covid-19).

The aim of the local CoPs is to facilitate learning and co-development of knowledge between the key stakeholders involved in the local demonstration cases. To achieve wider uptake of the solutions, the case owners need to gain and/or improve their knowledge on user needs and preferences, disseminate information about the solutions, build relationships with key stakeholders to further the implementation of the solutions, identify and address barriers and create pathways towards wider implementation. Thus, the more specific targets of the Local CoPs are to:

- Bring together selected stakeholders for each demonstration case with regard to wider uptake of the case solutions;
- Share required information and technical inputs to develop and promote the solutions in focus; and
- Explore and take steps to facilitate/develop IS based on the solutions.

To achieve this, the case owners rely, although to a varying degree, on involving a range of stakeholders outside the core members of the CoP. These stakeholders may include actors from all parts of the value chain, as well as other private sector players, relevant authorities, civil society, and media. Additionally, the CoP owners should strive to achieve a balance with respect to gender, youth, and ethnic background, to ensure that all relevant perspectives are included.

The interactions in the local CoP are best conducted face-to-face, especially at the initial stage. During the Covid-19 pandemic, this has not always been possible. The meetings have been, and will, for a large part be conducted in local language, to ease communication and relation-building.

Inspired by the approach in NextGen (Brouwer et al., 2018), we envisage a four inter-related step process through the project life course, where each step is associated with specific aims and activities to promote IS: :

- 1) Setting the scene – Conduct a stakeholder mapping to see which stakeholders they need to involve, visualise the current situation with regard to the solution in question, and set out future visions for the demonstration case (also with regard to circularity);
- 2) Closing the loop – Identify opportunities for closing their material cycle(s) and assess the bottlenecks and barriers in terms of feasibility and governance;
- 3) Implementation – Assess the circularity and sustainability of the solutions in question, and test possible business models; and
- 4) Upscaling and evaluation – Discuss potential policy recommendations for upscaling of the solutions and evaluate the CoPs impact on involved stakeholders throughout the project.

Figure 5 illustrates how this process may play out, with a more or less continuous flow of activity and regular work meetings centred on the demo case, providing input and

feedback to the supporting work packages, and at least one dedicated CoP meeting for each step in the process. These may be organised either as stand-alone events, or in combination with work packages and/or wider dissemination activities.

Figure 5: Schematic illustration of Local CoP process.

6.3 Project CoP process

In a way, all project participants in WIDER UPTAKE potentially constitute a CoP, to the extent that we share interest in research and innovation linked to the same domain, e.g., circular economy based on water resources, and interact regularly to build new ground in this area. The formal structures of communication and collaboration in the project, as defined through specified Work Packages and the Project Management Team, are the most crucial enablers of co-learning at this level. However, these are also, naturally, oriented towards specific Milestones and Deliverables.

The CoP approach, therefore, includes efforts to facilitate social learning also in the wider project. The project CoP targets are:

- Active networking and knowledge sharing between different stakeholders to facilitate interactions between researchers and non-researchers;
- To facilitate replication, knowledge transfer and lessons learned between and from the demo cases; and
- To promote the WIDER UPTAKE innovations and provide ideas and fruitful angles for promoting them also through the project dissemination activities.

The project CoP brings together different stakeholders: water utility operators and technology providers, but also other stakeholders such as relevant authorities, national water associations, NGOs, and R&D experts. The activity consists of cross-cutting CoP events organised by WP7, in liaison with WP1 and WP6, focusing on challenges and technologies/products/application modes that are cross-case relevant, placing the needs and experiences of the project user partners (utilities and other companies) centre stage.

Communication will take place in virtual or face to face meetings or workshops (such as WP-meetings or annual project meetings).

As stated in the Description of Action, the activities at this level may also include "mobile labs" or site visits where partners learn and develop new knowledge in the field, in connection with the demonstration activities.

6.4 Trans-Project CoP activities

The CoP activities at Trans-project level aim to create space for experience-sharing and knowledge transfer between WIDER UPTAKE and i) other projects under the Horizon2020 call "Water in the Context of the Circular Economy, ii) other relevant target groups, research communities and associations dealing with circular economy based on water resources. The targets are to

- Ensure collaboration and coordination with the other projects under the Horizon2020 programme "Water in the Context of the Circular Economy".
- Establish interaction with other international networks, initiatives/projects or research communities dealing with circular economy, enabling knowledge and methodological exchange, and
- Encourage dialogue on policy issues by facilitating debate, and expert elicitation and consultation across different sectors and circular economy strategies

Collaboration between the five "sister projects" under the mentioned call (WIDER UPTAKE, B-WaterSmart, ULTIMATE, REWAISE and WATER-MINING) is organised through regular meetings of the coordinators. These meetings take place on a quarterly basis with participation from REA (previously ESAME) who provide information and request inputs on policy issues, e.g., revision of EU directives, and events in the scope of the projects.

Otherwise, Trans-project CoP activities include participation of WIDER UPTAKE experts at events, conferences, exhibitions, or open sessions from other research associations. It also includes communication via online media (information via newsletter, homepage, social media, and cloud technology). Thus, it is closely linked with the Communication (T7.4) and Dissemination activities (WP6).

7 CoP management and support

7.1 CoPs as a joint responsibility

As stated in the Description of Action, it has been the responsibility of WP7 – Task 7.3 – to establish the CoPs in WIDER UPTAKE, as an organized structure for communication not only related to the project partners, but also open to mutual learning from and to other communities, to bridge boundaries, and promote a multi-stakeholder approach to facilitate water-smart solutions. This includes:

- Defining, supporting, and monitoring the CoP process at each demonstration site, to facilitate planning and co-ordination of the demonstration activities and support the integration and maximum added value of outcomes from the various sites.

This work is closely linked with that of WP1, which encompasses and coordinates all the demonstration activities, and where local research partners have the responsibility to follow up the demonstration at each respective demo site.

- Supporting externally oriented communication involving the local stakeholder groups.

This is a shared responsibility with Task 7.4 Communication, as well as Task 6.3 Dissemination, which is to ensure the widespread and transfer of the main results and knowledge provided by the project, with the aim to make results available for all the audience (stakeholders, academic, professionals, society, etc.) interested to them.

- Defining and implementing a process for project internal collaboration and learning, aside from regular work package meetings.

This may include virtual and physical workshops, use of the Virtual Sharing and Learning Centre to be established in WP6, as well as so-called "mobile labs", where knowledge is coproduced in the field.

- Supporting the Trans-project CoP activity.

The Trans-project CoP activity is mainly the responsibility of the Coordinator and Project Management Team, but rests upon the same perspective on learning and knowledge development as the other CoP activities.

7.2 Planning and launching of Local CoPs

Both in STOP-IT (Koti et al. 2017) and NextGen (Brouwer et al. 2018) the approach to CoPs is related to the recommendations for stakeholder participation provided by the OECD Water Governance Initiative (Akmouch & Clavreul 2016). These are as follows:

- **Inclusiveness and equity:** Map all stakeholders who have a stake in the outcome or that are likely to be affected, as well as their responsibility, core motivations and interactions.
- **Clarity of goals, transparency, and accountability:** Define the ultimate line of decision making, the objectives of stakeholder engagement and the expected use of inputs.
- **Capacity and information:** Allocate proper financial and human resources and share needed information for result-oriented stakeholder engagement.
- **Efficiency and effectiveness:** Regularly assess the process and outcomes of stakeholder engagement to learn, adjust and improve accordingly.
- **Institutionalisation, structuring and integration:** Embed engagement processes in clear legal and policy frameworks, organisational structures/principles, and responsible authorities.
- **Adaptiveness:** Customise the type and level of engagement as needed and keep the process flexible to changing circumstances.

These principles are at the basis of the WIDER UPTAKE approach as well. It should be noted, though, that the objective of the CoPs in our project is not stakeholder participation per se,

but rather to promote innovation uptake and realise more specific aims related to IS based on circular water solutions. While NextGen and more recent applications of the CoP concept by KWR (Andrews et al. 2021) place much emphasis on CoPs as platforms for stakeholder involvement, ensuring value, learning and relation-building in the core group is also crucially important. In WIDER UPTAKE, stakeholder engagement is achieved also via other project activities.

Amongst other based on the OECD recommendations, the following topics and questions were identified as crucial for the planning and launching of CoPs in STOP-IT (Koti et al. 2017). (Table 1):

Table 1: Key topics and questions for planning and launching CoPs (Koti et al. 2017).

Background and purpose	Key topics	Membership	Operating model	Behaviours
What is the local, regional, and global context the CoP will operate under?	Facilitate process, help specify main topic areas, challenges	Who are the key stakeholders?	How will the CoP meetings be organised?	What are the desired behaviours of the CoP?
What is the ambition, goal?	Who are the relevant bodies of knowledge?	Which organizations & individuals are to be invited (at what stage)?	What is the required/ desired duration of meetings?	What strategies should be taken to generate these behaviours?
What is the primary scope (learning, lobbying, marketing, etc)?	How will the flexibility of topics be ensured?	What are the professional experiences and org. positions of attendees?	How much time should members dedicate?	
What value does it bring to the members and the sector?	What types of knowledge do the different stakeholders bring?	What is needed to ensure the interest of the key stakeholders?	Who should manage and be the facilitator of the CoP?	

These have also been used in WIDER UPTAKE. However, one lesson learnt from STOP-IT was that some of the perspectives and concepts associated with CoPs may be unfamiliar and initially lack appeal among participants who mainly have a technical or business orientation (Mooren et al. 2021). Because of this, and also due to Covid-19 restrictions, the planning and launching of the Local CoPs took place in several steps.

Following a presentation on the CoPs during the virtual project kick-off, SINTEF established a live background document on the approach in WIDER UPTAKE. The essence of this document was then boiled down to a 2-pager (Annex 1).

The 2-pager was discussed with the partners in charge of each demo case in initial meetings to identify how best to launch the Local CoP in each case. We also had a group discussion, drawing on a set of questions derived from the World Bank Group (2017, p. 51-53), also presented in Brouwer et al. (2018), as a useful instrument when launching CoPs. The initial workshops and further process in each case are described in chapter 7.

7.3 Management and support of Local CoPs

Before the initial Local CoP workshops a *CoP manager* from one of the partners in the respective demo case was identified. The initial *Core group* was defined as the key stakeholders identified in the Description of Action. The distribution for the different cases is listed below (Table 2):

Table 2: Local CoPs, core groups and roles.

Local CoP	CoP Manager	Core group	Facilitating research partner
Sicily	UNIPA (Giorgio Mannina)	AMAP SPA (utility) Corleone and Marineo Municipalities	UNIPA
Hamar	HIAS (Morten Finborud)	Hias IKS (water utility) Hias How2O (technology provider) Sirkula (waste management) NTNU	SINTEF
Stavanger	IVAR (Leif Ydstebø ¹)	IVAR IKS (water utility) Grønn Vekst (recycling organic resources) Lyse (energy company) NTNU	SINTEF
Czech Republic	CTU (Jaroslav Pollert)	PVK a.s.(utility) PVS a.s (utility), Prague City Council, local municipalities Storm Aqua (provider of blue-green solutions)	UCT
Netherlands	NPSP (Mark Lepelaar ²)	Waternet (water utility) NPSP (producer of biocomposite materials) TU Delft	SINTEF
Ghana	CSIR-STEPRI (Gordon Akon-Yamga)	Sewerage Systems Ghana Limited (utility) Urban Farmers Association CSIR Water Research Institute CSIR- Institute for Industrial Research	CSIR-STEPRI

As shown in Table 2, each CoP also got a *Facilitating research partner* assigned to it. In most cases, this is a local partner, who also speaks the local language. One exception is the Dutch case, where SINTEF is involved. In three of the cases, Ghana, Sicily and the Czech Republic, the local research partner is also the CoP Manager since the research partner is orchestrating the demo case.

The role of the *CoP manager* is to help the community focus on its domain, maintain relationships and develop its practice related to the aims for the project and respective demonstration case.

¹ Has since left IVAR and been replaced by Geir Skogerbø.

² Since replaced by Peter van Gilst, who has been hired by NPSP and Waternet (50/50) to work on WIDER UPTAKE.

The role of the *Facilitating research partner* is to help create the desired outcome by providing assistance, guidance or supervision, and link with the WP activities and resources developed in WIDER UPTAKE.

In practice, the Facilitating research partner may take quite different roles, depending on the pre-existing relations between the core members, what the perceived challenges and visions of the respective CoP are, and the local cultural context. Proposing new legislation, which is a stated aim in the Sicilian case, requires dialogue with policy makers, where a certain level of formality and emphasis on researchers as "experts" is appropriate, whereas the focus on business case development and symbiosis among a smaller group of specified actors, such as in the Dutch case, may require a more informal, "bottom-up" approach. The *Core group*, coordinated by the CoP manager, is responsible for defining the focus and goal/s of the CoP and mapping the potential stakeholders that could or should be involved at different stages. Wider CoP participants, active and more peripheral, are in turn be invited based on the following:

- Relationship of organization with core group and/or other stakeholders;
- Relevant activities when it comes to CE based on water resources;
- Relation of the organization to the water sector and WIDER UPTAKE;
- Hierarchical position of invited person within the organization represented; and
- Known enthusiasm and knowledge of invited person with regards to the CoP mission.

As CoPs are designed to be flexible, the scopes and goals may adapt over the duration of the project, due to the needs identified in the respective communities. Thereby, the relevant stakeholders and their respective roles may also change over time.

7.4 Management of project and trans-project CoP activity

The project CoP is managed under *WP7*. The *Coordinator* and *Project Management Team* have the ultimate responsibility. WP leaders are responsible for including and informing partners based on their respective roles and interests, as well as contributing to social learning in the wider project.

Task 7.3, which is led by SINTEF but includes all project partners, is responsible for proposing and organising dedicated CoP activities, in collaboration with the PMT, in form of virtual and physical workshops and "mobile labs", where the partners co-produce knowledge during visits to the project demonstration sites, centred on specific solutions, experiments and/or tools developed in the WPs.

The trans-project CoP activities are managed by the *Coordinator* and *Project Management Team* and supported by *T7.3*. *WP6* is responsible for providing seminars on specific topics regarding the project (wastewater reuse, nutrients recovery, PHA extraction, etc.), targeting relevant stakeholders as well as young researchers. It will also organize summer schools, with lectures by recognized experts in the specific topics investigated by the project. Furthermore, *WP6* has a Task dedicated to engagement activities with entrepreneurs, investors, the regulators, and the policy makers in Ghana, including seminars, workshops, demonstrations, field visits, participation in fairs and exhibitions, among others.

T7.2 includes provision of communication materials and efforts to raise awareness among politicians, regulatory authorities, while T7.3 is to support external oriented communication involving the local stakeholder groups.

7.5 Overview of resources and infrastructure

To support the local CoPs, a number of resources have been made available. First, the mentioned *background document* (early version of the present text) was developed, including information and reference to further literature on Communities of Practice as a learning concept, as well as examples of how it has been applied in other EU projects, and an initial sketch of the approach for WIDER UPTAKE. The document was made available to all project partners via Microsoft Teams. Based on the background document, a more accessible *two-pager* was made, for easy reference, distribution when inviting potential members, etc.

Templates for Local CoP workshop reports, to keep record of outcomes and process developments and facilitate learning across the different CoPs and in relation to the wider project, have been provided. Likewise, *Workshop evaluation forms* (further described in chapter 8) have been made available.

Furthermore, SINTEF initiated a *Project calendar*, where all partners have been strongly encouraged to enter planned activities and events, to ease coordination and provide predictability. This is important, both to avoid overloading the water utilities and private companies with information and feedback requests in certain periods, and to help ensure that Local CoPs receive support and inputs as needed, enabling continuity and a desirable "rhythm" in each case, (Wenger et al. (2002). The calendar may also help identify the most suitable times for project- and trans-project CoP activities.

A *List of CoP moderation tools*, collected in STOP-IT and presented publicly in Brouwer et al. 2018) has been made available on Teams.

While other projects, e.g., ULTIMATE and WATER-MINING, have developed guidelines with a wide array of templates, check lists and procedures (Andrews et al. 2021), WIDER UPTAKE places more emphasis on adaptiveness than structuring (Akmouch & Clavreul 2016). Customization and culture sensitivity is needed to ensure that a sense of ownership and engagement is maintained to keep the process flexible to changing circumstances. This may be particularly important where the aim relates to IS, and not merely development and dissemination on specific project outcomes and solutions.

In the Netherlands and Norway, the initial workshops were conducted in collaboration with the local utilities – Waternet (Netherlands), Hias (Hamar) and IVAR (Stavanger) and SINTEF. SINTEF is also available for support in the planning, organizing, facilitation of meetings, etc. in the other cases, but here the local research partners have taken the lead. They know the local partners and their context best. The ability to conduct meetings etc. in the local language is important, both in Sicily and the Czech Republic. In Ghana, English is one of the official languages and the most common *lingua franca*, although *Twi* or a mix often is preferred.

With a view to language and local sense of ownership WIDER UPTAKE websites using local language have been established both in the Czech Republic, and in Sicily, where Linked-In, Twitter and Facebook are also used to promote the local CoP.

Starting from month 18, a Virtual Learning and Sharing Centre (VLSC) will be developed in WP6, providing a resource for both project- and trans-project CoP development. An overview of the resources and infrastructure provided for each CoP level is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Resources and infrastructure provided for the CoP activities.

Resources/ Infrastructure	Available / Recommended resources / infrastructure at CoP-level		
	Local	Project	Trans-project
Resources (time and personnel)	Preparation, participation and reporting of local workshops <i>(case owner/utility with support from local research partner and T7.3)</i>	Preparation, participation and reporting of task-leader, WP- or project meetings, STC-meetings etc. <i>(whole consortium)</i>	Participation at conferences, workshops, and events Exchange with other research communities <i>(Coordinator, selected experts from WIDER UPTAKE)</i>
IT-structure for information exchange	Teams, project websites in local language (Sicily, Czech Republic), VLSC (WP6)	Teams, Virtual Learning and Sharing Centre (to be provided from WP6)	Announcements, news, ongoing activities via 1.WU homepage, LinkedIn, (T7.4) 2.Teams, VLSC (WP6)
Coordination & Technical Support	1. Guidance on launching and management of the CoP in terms of what to do by whom, when and how to do it (T7.3) 2. Central coordination of local workshops providing timeline and frame of workshops (T7.3, with WP1 and T7.2)	Guidance on launching the CoP in terms of what to do by whom, when and how to do it (T7.3, T7.2)	Guidance in terms of what to do by whom, when and how to do it T7.4, WP6, T7.3, T7.2

As the table shows, resources and infrastructure for the CoPs are to be provided not only via Task 7.3, but also from other tasks and WPs in the project.

8 CoP monitoring

Although CoPs are used widely, there is insufficient focus and a lack of consensus on how to evaluate their outputs (Lorenz & Barlatier 2007). Fulgenzi et al (2020) note that qualitative approaches tend to be resource-intensive and retrospective, while quantitative methods fail to address social learning adequately.

Ai Yu, who carried out a research-based evaluation for the African Development Bank in 2009, suggests that demand for CoPs is driven by (i) socio-psychological needs, (ii) professional-structural needs, and (iii) institutional-operational needs, and that they therefore may be analysed or measured according to these. Measures considered relevant for the socio-psychological dimension and "community" development are level of awareness (measured by degree common interests, sense of belonging, willingness to take part, and experiencing a welcoming ambience. Concerning the professional-structural dimension, having a clear domain, leveraging knowledge management tools, generating tangible communal resources (such as a user-friendly communication platform) and experienced work relevance are proposed (Yu 2009). As to the institutional-operational dimension, perceptions of leadership, ease of entry and participation, evidence of strategic thinking and resource allocation are suggested indicators (ibid.)

Fulgenzi et al (2020) developed an assessment framework based on the conception that CoP development can be understood as the parallel development of CoP dimensions (community, domain, and practice) and social learning outcomes (relation-building, shared understanding, and substantive outcome, e.g., change in knowledge among the individuals involved). Relating the two dimensions, they identify three key elements that are crucial and should be in focus in CoP evaluation:

- a) engagement and interaction of stakeholders,
- b) change in stakeholders issue frames, and
- c) stakeholder awareness of their own and other members' roles and competences

Based on literature and dialogue with four CoP facilitators, they came up with six key success factors:

- 1) organizational support
- 2) atmosphere of the meeting
- 3) representation and engagement
- 4) convergence on a shared perspective
- 5) identification of opportunities and challenges
- 6) co-generation of knowledge

Each of these are associated with a set of indicators that address specific CoP dynamics and provide a quantitative measurement, in the sense that a Likert-type questionnaire with scores from 1-5 is administered to participants.

On the other hand, the approach initially defined in STOP-IT (Koti et al. 2017)³ consists of a set of more open qualitative questions:

- What are the outcomes of the workshops/meetings?
- What are the outcomes of the CoP?
- What is the impact of materials produced/meetings/workshops?
- Have there been any actions taken by members of the CoP in their organizations, as result of the CoP?
- What is the relation between the CoP's outcomes and the outcomes of the organizations represented?

³ The approach from Fulgenzi et al (2020) was adopted in the second half of the project (Mooren et al. 2021).

- What are the small wins of the CoP?

While Fulgenzi et al. (2020) focus mainly on the process of CoP development, the evaluative questions initially used in STOP-IT put more emphasis on the outcomes and achievements of the CoPs. On this background, and also realising that questionnaires for systematic monitoring rarely are filled by all participants, WIDER UPTAKE has taken a "middle way", recognizing the success criteria identified by Fulgenzi et al. (2016), while limiting the number of indicators and defining them in a way that puts more emphasis on outcomes. The criteria and indicators for evaluation and monitoring of the Local CoPs are presented below (Table 4).

Table 4: Criteria and indicators for evaluation and monitoring of the Local CoPs.

Criteria	Indicators
Organizational support	Adequate planning and execution
Atmosphere enabling stakeholder interaction and engagement	Nurturing existing relationships
	Providing opportunity for new connections
	Conducive atmosphere
Representation and room for dialogue	Inclusion of all relevant perspectives
	Opportunity for participants to voice their opinions and concerns
Convergence	Common conclusions
	Change/expansion of own perspective
Identification of opportunities and challenges	Identification of joint actions, follow-ups
	Identification of actions, follow-ups in own organisation
Co-generation of knowledge	Increased knowledge
	Increased awareness

These criteria and indicators are applied in the provided workshop evaluation form for Local CoP workshops, to be distributed and collected at the closing of each event (Annex 2). Here, the mentioned indicators are translated into more specific questions, to be answered via a 1-5 Likert scale, with space for additional comments.

For the Project CoP activities, the form of interaction, topics and type of outcomes will vary considerably (e.g., across different types of meetings organised by the WPs, webinars, mobile labs, plenary project meetings etc). The dedicated Project CoP activities will be evaluated based on:

- 1) Attendance (number of participants)
- 2) Range of participants (if they are attended by both researchers and practitioners, from different countries)
- 3) Relevance (feedback from participants and PMT, during and after the events)

4) Achievement of the targets set out for the Project CoP

Record of activities at the Trans-project CoP level will be kept and evaluated qualitatively by the PMT, in relation to

- 1) Achievement of the identified targets for the trans-CoP activity
- 2) Their contribution towards the targeted impacts of WIDER UPTAKE as a whole

The following chapter presents an overview and summary evaluation of the CoP activities that have taken place so far.

9 CoP activity up to M18

9.1 Local CoP, Sicily

The local actors related with the Italian case studies (Marineo and Corleone wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are mainly represented by agricultural companies, interested in water, nutrients, and composted sludge reuse, environmental associations, company interested in bioplastic reuse, municipalities owner of the WWTPs. These actors represent the key stakeholders that are part of the CoP. The above-mentioned companies are all located in the province of Palermo.

Launching workshop

The launching workshop was held on 8th of July 2020 at the Palermo University. High level political representatives and participants from University of Palermo were present. The distribution among different categories of participants is shown below (Table 5).

Table 5: Participation at first Local CoP workshop in Palermo.

Institution / sector	No. of participants		
	In total	Male	Female
Authorities	4	4	
Representatives of companies, other sectors	4	4	
UNIPA, Dept. of Engineering	4	3	1
UNIPA, Dept. of Agricultural, Food and Forest Science	2	2	
UNIPA, Dept. of Biological, Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technologies	2	2	
UNIPA, Law Department	3	3	

The stakeholders highlighted the interest to modify the local regulations in accordance with the circular economy concept. The demonstration of the feasibility of smart water solutions is particularly important to break existing social and administrative barriers.

The role of the Office of the Special Unique Commissioner in the Sicilian territory concerning the Wastewater Treatment facilities was emphasized. The responsibility of the Commissioner is to carry out necessary actions related to design and construction.

Further process

After the initial meeting, several meetings were organised (monthly), between UNIPA and AMAP Spa to discuss how to modify the facilities.

To address the social and administrative barriers to new water solutions, the Special Unique Commissioner, and the Sicilian President of the national association of Italian municipalities (ANCI) signed a memorandum of understanding after the Wider Uptake Launch in July 2020. The memorandum aims to create a network for breaking the existing administrative barriers regarding the application of Smart Solutions in the Wastewater sub-sector.

On 23rd of December 2020 a workshop between UNIPA, AMAP SpA and Angelo Schiavone (project manager for the revamping of Corleone WWTP) was held with the aim of sharing and addressing future design choices for the application of water smart solutions. Specifically, how to reduce sludge production and energy requirements was discussed and planned.

A webinar entitled "The role of Governance in water purification - presentation of the GOCIWA tool" was organized on 15th of June 2021. The webinar aimed to present the tool developed in WP4 and discuss the first results of its application to the cases of Marineo and Corleone.

The presenters and main participants included four representatives of the local authorities and representatives of AMAP, as well as from different departments at UNIPA. Giorgio Mannina, as local CoP manager, led the event, as shown below (Figure 6). The webinar was followed by 61 users.

Figure 6: Giorgio Mannina presenting at Local CoP webinar in Sicily 15th June 2021. Photo: Alida Cosenza.

More recently (14 September 2021) prof Mannina met with the President of the territorial water assembly (ATI) and the Director of the water and waste district of the Sicilian Region to solve the existing problems that hinder the water reuse in Corleone.”

Feedback and evaluation

As reported, all participants have been very enthusiastic and appreciated the purpose of the meetings. While face-to-face interaction in periods has been limited by Covid-19 restrictions, the stakeholders have also suggested to have more frequent meetings and discuss/share solutions.

A strong collaboration among UNIPA, AMAP Spa and the Municipalities of Marineo and Corleone (key stakeholders) have currently occurred. The two main partners are collaborating to implement the WWTPs modernisation by adopting the water smart solutions required to move towards a circular economy model. These changes were agreed upon during the previous meetings, aimed at discussing the critical points to be addressed in the structural planning and to identify the priority actions.

The Local CoP has a vision to demonstrate and put the water reuse facility into operation and propose a new regulation for water reuse in Sicily, and both aims are systematically addressed. Increasing public awareness is also in focus, which is the main reason for establishing the local project website.

Going forward, it is important to keep the agricultural companies as well as wider stakeholders in the loop, so that value chain development can be worked upon in parallel. This may also get easier as the demonstration progresses, and Covid-19 restrictions are lifted. Furthermore, these aspects will also be addressed through interaction with Task 4.2, on network development and exploration of new business models.

With respect to participation and gender balance, it is noted that most participants and presenters are male. While this may reflect the present distribution in the relevant sectors, conscious attempt will be made to also include competent female speakers, in future. A summary evaluation by the facilitating research partner is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Summary evaluation by facilitating research partner, Local CoP in Sicily.

Criteria	Indicators	Reflections
Organizational support	Adequate planning and execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meetings organization Facilitation of the communication between stakeholders
Atmosphere enabling stakeholder interaction and engagement	Nurturing existing relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We promote interaction between other project partners and stakeholders Social networking
	Providing opportunity for new connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The organized meeting is opportunity for interaction with stakeholders
	Conducive atmosphere	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Events organization

Representation and room for dialogue	Inclusion of all relevant perspectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meetings and workshops organization
	Opportunity for participants to voice their opinions and concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Future workshop and brainstorming between partners and stakeholders
Convergence	Common conclusions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Necessity to find a way for the wastewater resource recovery Implement the industrial symbiosis
	Change/expansion of own perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possibility to use alternative sources in agriculture and in other sectors (e.g., biopolymers)
Identification of opportunities and challenges	Identification of joint actions, follow-ups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Newsletters sent by the principal partner to stakeholders
	Identification of actions, follow-ups in own organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possibility to develop a brand to promote the internal market
Generation of knowledge	Increased knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organization of workshops, meetings, and seminars Collaboration with schools to promote a change of mind
	Increased awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Safety problems related to the reuse of some WRRF products The absence of a market for the recovered products

9.2 Local CoP, Hamar

Launching workshop

The initial meeting was held on September 28th, 2020, at the premises of HIAS at Hamar. The core group has a history of collaboration and know each other well, but parts of the research team and the idea of collaborating as a CoP were new to them. Due to Covid-19, the number of participants at the initial meeting was restricted to a minimum, distributed as follows (Table 7):

Table 7: Participation at first Local CoP workshop in Hamar.

Institution / sector	No. of participants		
	In total	Male	Female
Authorities	0		
HIAS	1	1	
HIAS How2O	1	1	
Sirkula	2	1	1
SINTEF Community (water chemist)	1	1	
SINTEF Digital (social scientists)	2	1	1

WPI leader and main contact for the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) was also invited but could not attend. The workshop was a full-day event, including a tour through the facilities at both HIAS and Sirkula (Figure 7), as well as presentations by all parties and discussion of the CoP format and objectives.

HIAS is already recovering biogas, which is sold and used as fuel, amongst others for specialised waste transportation trucks operated by Sirkula. HIAS has also carried out a pilot on biological phosphorous removal (Bio-P) and aims to realize a full-scale phosphorous recovery plant and use sludge to provide peat-free soil products in collaboration with Sirkula. This is their main priority in WIDER UPTAKE, together with improving the framework conditions for circular economy linked to water and waste. Struvite is approved as a mineral fertilizer with organic origin in Norway. The utility wants to see new value chains for struvite and biomass, which go beyond the traditional way of thinking in the sector. HIAS How20 has been established as a subsidiary and separate provider of nutrient recovery technologies, with international ambitions. The manager noted that over the 4-year project period, around five new projects to implement their patented HIAS-process should be generated.

Sirkula has been an early mover in waste management and is keen to contribute to the development of innovative bioeconomy in the region. Its main priority in WIDER UPTAKE is soil production with input from HIAS. The aim is to be able to produce soil that is entirely without peat and develop the value chain as much as possible. The amount of garden- and wood waste received is enough to produce around 30 000 tons of peat-free soil per year.

Figure 7: Tour of facilities at the initial Local CoP workshop in Hamar. Left: Senior Staff at HIAS, in front of pilot struvite unit. Right: Director Grethe Olsbye and colleague in front of soil products. Photos: Sigrid Damman.

The local actors highlighted some of the remaining barriers that WIDER UPTAKE should address, namely conservative practices when it comes to public procurement, uncertainties concerning future regulations and framework conditions, and limited acceptance among farmers. At the same time, creating awareness, both among potential users, the general public and relevant authorities, was seen as important. The national discourse on CE has had a much stronger focus on other sectors than wastewater. To address these issues, the Local CoP will involve other stakeholders gradually, including local and regional authorities,

Norwegian Water, the national association for waste management companies (Avfall Norge), the national Farmers' Association, Centre for Ecological Agriculture, etc.

Together, the partners want to make a common showcase, with three important aspects: 1) develop a value chain for struvite, 2) new knowledge of application of biomass with less costs/avoid costs, and 3) new knowledge and arguments to influence framework conditions.

Further process

At the launching workshop the local partners planned to meet every two weeks. Due to Covid-19 and other factors they were not able to keep this schedule, but they have interacted regularly. In connection with the struvite plant an agreement has been established with the entrepreneur ENWA, with a sub-supplier agreeing to a flexible arrangement for distribution of the product. An MoU has also been entered with a local soil-producing company, which therefore may be considered part of the active CoP group. Moreover, HIAS has been active in the national dialogue on the future organization of water and wastewater services, amongst other through a Working Group in Norwegian Water, which delivered a report on this in June 2021. HIAS and HIAS How20 also gave a detailed update on their demonstration case at a virtual project CoP meeting in June 2021 (further described in section 9.7).

Feedback and evaluation

Although the CoP concept was unfamiliar, the evaluation of the launching workshop was very positive. The local partners are collaborating actively and clearly capable and determined to drive the process locally. Progress towards the stated aims for the Local CoP has also been achieved. On the other hand, a sense of ownership to the CoP concept has not really developed. Going forward, it will be of mutual benefit to work more actively with this concept. In the coming phase, when the struvite facility is put in place and the need to develop a market for the product comes more into focus, a wider range of stakeholders will be addressed. This may also include more direct collaboration with the Local CoP linked to the Stavanger/IVAR demonstration case. A summary evaluation of the formal Local CoP activities in Hamar is presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Summary evaluation of Local CoP in Hamar at Month 18, by facilitating research partner.

Criteria	Indicators	Reflections
Organizational support	Adequate planning and execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop went well All partners were well prepared, although the CoP concept was unfamiliar the objectives were clear
Atmosphere enabling stakeholder interaction and engagement	Nurturing existing relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very fruitful, especially for relation-building between the local industry partners and research partners in WU (external stakeholders not invited due to Covid-19 restrictions)
	Providing opportunity for new connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> So far only inside WU, restricted participation due to Covid-19
	Conducive atmosphere	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nice and amicable, informal. Touring the facilities at HIAS and Sirkula was also useful in this respect.
Representation and room for dialogue	Inclusion of all relevant perspectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The perspectives of all actors were equally presented, as were different disciplines.
	Opportunity for participants to voice their opinions and concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes, there was enough time for discussion and all parties participated actively and openly.
Convergence	Common conclusions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common conclusions were reached, vision to become a national competence centre for CE based on water and waste resources
	Change/expansion of own perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced understanding of learning and collaboration opportunities in WIDER UPTAKE
Identification of opportunities and challenges	Identification of joint actions, follow-ups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explore market opportunities for struvite. Contribute to national discourse on CE based on water resources, policy, and legal-administrative barriers.
	Identification of actions, follow-ups in own organisation	
Generation of knowledge	Increased knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Useful exchange on technological matters linked to demo case and market situation for the HIAS process.
	Increased awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On CoP collaboration (benefits and challenges), drivers and barriers, opportunities for cross-learning between the cases in the project

9.3 Local CoP, Stavanger

Launching workshop

The initial workshop for the Local CoP in Stavanger was held on October 6th, 2020, at IVAR's head office at Forus, and rounded off with a visit to the wastewater treatment plant at Mekjarvik, where the Minorga fertiliser is produced (Figure 8). Due to Covid-19, the number of participants was restricted in this case, too. As shown in Table 9, IVAR and Grønn Vekst was present together with research representatives from SINTEF. NTNU will also have a crucial role to play but was absent with apologies this time.

Table 9: Distribution of participants at the initial Local CoP workshop in Stavanger.

Institution / sector	No. of participants		
	In total	Male	Female
IVAR	3	1	2
Grønn Vekst	1	1	
SINTEF Community (water chemist)	1	1	
SINTEF Digital (social scientists)	2	1	1

Aims in WIDER UPTAKE on the side of IVAR are to optimize the process solutions and see how struvite may be taken into the fertilizer production. The system and method are different from that at HIAS, but the two utilities also think similarly in many ways. Two important differences are that the Stavanger region has a gas grid, where biogas from IVAR is injected, and that the struvite can be used in the existing fertilizer production.

Grønn Vekst is a leading company in Norway in management of organic and mineral by-products, and together with IVAR co-owners of Minorga AS, a joint venture established for the production and sale of fertilizers. Minorga is based on sludge, primarily from the WWTP at Mekjarvik, where 5000 tons of dry matter/20 000 tons of sludge are produced.

So far, Vietnam is the main market for Minorga. For the domestic market, variable zinc levels have been a challenge, but the product is currently approved for use also in Norway. However, limited acceptance is a challenge. Measuring of heavy metals and field experiments to address these challenges are ongoing, and one of the ambitions for the case in WIDER UPTAKE is to increase acceptability and work to develop new intelligent fertilizers.

An initial reaction from IVAR was that they are not so used to this way of thinking, that is, working with a CoP to facilitate CE, build networks and develop value chains. The common vision for the local CoP was not immediately clear but defined during the workshop as: a) Find a solution to technical challenges related to struvite production at Mekjarvik, b) enhance biogas production, c) get more dialogue with potential users of Minorga.

Figure 8: Participants at Local CoP workshop 6th October 2020, in front of one of IVAR's WWTPs.
Photo: Sigrid Damman.

Further process

As in the other cases, the interaction in the Local CoP in Stavanger since the launching workshop has been influenced by Covid-19. In addition, there have been unforeseen challenges, in that the appointed CoP manager left IVAR for another job. There has also been a change of ownership at Grønn Vekst, whereby key resource persons for their work in WIDER UPTAKE have established a separate company called Terramarine. Grønn Vekst is still the WIDER UPTAKE partner and has found a way to include the key persons since before. However, the joint venture for Minorga is dissolved, and IVAR is now the sole producer, while Grønn Vekst and Terramarine are distributors and designers of the fertilisers. Currently, sludge from aquaculture is also mixed into the sludge from IVAR, as part of the product development.

While transportation costs have increased during the Covid-19 pandemic, the organizational changes have caused uncertainty concerning future strategies. The CoP as such did not have much contact in the first half of 2021. The new main contact for IVAR had most focus on the technical demonstrations, and IVAR made an excellent contribution to the Project CoP workshop on struvite in June. By September, when SINTEF requested another workshop with the Local CoP, a pre-meeting was held, to clarify the objectives and ensure that relevant personnel were included.

The second dedicated CoP workshop was a two-day event, 4-5 October. In line with the four-step process discussed above (section 6.2), its objective was to further discuss opportunities to increase circularity and assess the bottlenecks and barriers in terms of feasibility and governance. Thus, there were discussions on technical development, results

from the initial governance assessment carried out by WP4, as well as conceptions and criteria for measuring water smartness (as input to WP5).

Feedback and evaluation

While the atmosphere was amicable, the evaluation forms from the second workshop indicated that there is a need for relation-building and more effort for all to see the value of interdisciplinary collaboration in the CoP format. The above-mentioned uncertainties influence the process, in that some issues remain sensitive. However, all participants stated that it was quite important to meet. How to optimise the recovery and use of resources from sludge is still a common focus. Looking forward, dialogue with Norwegian Water in connection with their effort to provide national sludge strategy, and closer contact with the CoP in Hamar were two specific actions identified. The workshop will also be followed up with another iteration on the framework for assessing water smartness (WP5) and activity related to IS network and business model development in WP4. A summary evaluation of the process so far is provided in Table 10.

Table 10: Summary evaluation of Local CoP activity in Stavanger by month 18, provided by facilitating research partner.

Criteria	Indicators	Reflections
Organizational support	Adequate planning and execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshops went well, all partners well prepared Since inter-disciplinary, even more effort could be made to communicate objectives, main issues in advance
Atmosphere enabling stakeholder interaction and engagement	Nurturing existing relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very fruitful, both for relation-building in WU and between local partners, where new persons were brought in during Covid-19
	Providing opportunity for new connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> So far only inside WU, restricted participation due to Covid-19
	Conducive atmosphere	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nice and amicable, informal. May think of localising meetings to different partners, as who is the host influences dynamics.
Representation and room for dialogue	Inclusion of all relevant perspectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The perspectives of all actors were equally presented, as were different disciplines.
	Opportunity for participants to voice their opinions and concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes, ample time for discussion and nobody cut short.
Convergence	Common conclusions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common conclusions were reached
	Change/expansion of own perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CoP activities help formulate our perspectives in more realistic ways
Identification of opportunities and challenges	Identification of joint actions, follow-ups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes, there were. At most recent workshop to invite collaboration with Hamar CoP

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initiate dialogue with Norwegian Water project to develop national sludge strategy
	Identification of actions, follow-ups in own organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Points above to be followed up.
Generation of knowledge	Increased knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Useful exchange on technological matters linked to demo case and market situation for Minorga
	Increased awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On CoP collaboration (benefits and challenges), drivers and barriers, notion of 'water smartness'

9.4 Local CoP, Ghana

Launching workshop

The initial meeting in the Ghana CoP was held on October 30th, 2020, at the premises of CSIR-STEPRI in Accra (Figure 9). The distribution of participants at the workshop is presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Participants at Local CoP launching workshop in Accra, October 2020.

Institution / sector	No. of participants		
	In total	Male	Female
Authorities	7	4	3
Representatives of companies, other sectors	3	1	2
Internal stakeholders (not members of WIDER UPTAKE)	15	11	4
WIDER UPTAKE members	13	10	3

The objective of the meeting was to establish a local CoP and to enlighten the CoP members about the WIDER UPTAKE project, and in particular the Accra case. In addition, the CoP meeting aimed to provide participants with knowledge about the core processes and solutions addressed in the demonstration case, and through this obtain specific inputs for the implementation.

Together, the participants agreed on technical- and process objectives of the CoP. Technical objectives are to show the capacity of CoP towards innovative, technical solutions that optimize wastewater reuse, resource recovery and energy utilization. Furthermore, the CoP aims to engender discussion around the technical aspect of the demonstration case vis-à-vis the production of biochar and wastewater treatment process at Mudor Wastewater Treatment plant.

Possibilities and intended actions to be taken were discussed. The vast potential for wastewater reuse for agriculture and biochar in Ghana was highlighted. Biochar is crucial to reduce the use of wood for charcoal production and hence, deforestation. To do so by involving the private sector in the project is seen as important, as well as creating awareness

around the prospects of wastewater reuse and biochar production and use as a replacement for wood-based charcoal is also of national importance.

While ensuring a successful demonstration and co-developing the innovations at SSGL is one main ambition, the other is to contribute to identifying and removing barriers that may hinder the scaling-up of the innovations. Based on these, the vision of Ghana's CoP is to co-develop and promote the use of CE solutions from wastewater treatment.

Figure 9: Participants at the first Local CoP workshop in Ghana, including coordinator Herman Helness on the screen to the right. Photos: Gordon Akon-Yamga.

Further process

The achievement of the ambitions will depend on the ability of the CoP to address three key challenges. First, the challenge of addressing the policy gaps in respect of promoting CE solutions in the country; second, the challenge of producing safe solutions that meet local and international standards; and third, the challenge of supplying the innovations to the end-users in a safe and inexpensive manner.

Since the first CoP meeting, there have been follow-up meetings among the core members including CSIR (CSIR-STEPRI, CSIR-WRI, and CSIR-IIR), SSGL, Food and Drugs Authority (FDA), Ghana Standards Authority, and Vegetable Farmers Association.

Feedback and evaluation

The participants at the initial workshop in Ghana appreciated its informative and interactive nature. They also found it well-coordinated with clear presentations and high level of understanding of workshop objectives and outcomes, with varied stakeholder participation. On the other hand, it was noted that more time could be set aside for discussions. CSIR-STEPRI notes that the core group needs to be augmented to include city authorities (Accra Metropolitan Assembly), the Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development, and the Ministry of Environment Science Technology and Innovation (MESTI). Going forward, the CoP in Ghana needs to adopt a structure with a chairperson and secretary and regularised meetings to allow for more interactions and follow-ups. A summary evaluation of the activity up to month 18, by the facilitating research partner, is provided in Table 12.

Table 12: Summary evaluation of Local CoP activity in Ghana, by the facilitating research partner.

Criteria	Indicators	Reflections
Organizational support	Adequate planning and execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitations to meetings were done in advance and this allowed for more partners to attend • Members/partners actively participated in the CoP meetings
Atmosphere enabling stakeholder interaction and engagement	Nurturing existing relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The atmosphere afforded the partners, especially, WWTP (Sewerage Systems Ghana Limited-SSGL), regulators (e.g., Ghana Standards Authority-GSA and EPA) and policymakers (Ministry of Environment Science Technology and Innovation) to interact in relation to the innovations (biochar and treated wastewater). Ordinarily, they may interact, but not specifically on the innovations. • Subsequent to the interactions, there have not been independent bilateral interactions (not at the behest of the project) between the WWTP and some of the members (e.g., GSA)
	Providing opportunity for new connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The CoP is very instrumental in not only facilitating the connection of actors to each other, but it also enabled the actors to focus on a different agenda than usual—the innovations. • CoP provided opportunity for farmers to interact with research institutions with respect to testing of their produce for certification
	Conducive atmosphere	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meetings were often at the CSIR-STEPRI where most of the actors knew and had attended meetings before. • The atmosphere created by actors' presence was also conducive for deliberations
Representation and room for dialogue	Inclusion of all relevant perspectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are different categories of stakeholders participating in the CoP (WWTP, regulators, researchers, users of innovations, and policymakers)
	Opportunity for participants to voice their opinions and concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The atmosphere was very conducive for participants to express their opinions without fear or favour. • Facilitations on meetings is aimed to ensure that the atmosphere is accommodating of all views. Even where a local language must be spoken, it was done to ensure that some of the farmers understood proceedings

Convergence	Common conclusions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The CoP decisions and conclusions were unanimous, carrying onboard and reflecting deliberations
	Change/expansion of own perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Following from the CoP activities, we have come to realise that we need to change our approach to the dissemination of research information.
Identification of opportunities and challenges	Identification of joint actions, follow-ups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The need to actively engage the city authorities and the media The need for each stakeholder to influence behavioural change at their organizations Establish a more regular means of communicating and interacting
	Identification of actions, follow-ups in own organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure that members in-house are fully engaged and aware of all aspects of the project and therefore of CoP activities
Generation of knowledge	Increased knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased knowledge about effective means to communicate research to the stakeholders Knowledge of relevant stakeholders to engage in developing the innovations.
	Increased awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased awareness of the socio-political terrain that we need to navigate in order to promote the innovations Awareness about the demand for the biochar innovation

9.5 Local CoP, Prague

Initial meeting

The process started with an online meeting between CTU and SINTEF 16.09.2020, to develop a common understanding internally before introducing other local stakeholders to the CoP- concept. Since PVS, as the Prague water utility, has limited time for this type of activities, it was decided that CTU, represented by Prof. Jaroslav Pollert would be the Local CoP owner, and that selected participants from CTU, UCT and PVS would start as core members.

There were some questions on how to involve StormAqua since this is a Norway-based company and there were strict travel restrictions due to Covid-19. Although StormAqua has highly relevant products, they were not involved with the Czech partners before matching up in WIDER UPTAKE. Another crucial stakeholder is the City of Prague, but due to Covid-19, the Municipality was closed at the time. It was also noted that stakeholder involvement is different and a less established practice than in other countries, such as Germany, so there is a need to tread carefully and ensure that the objectives and the value of the CoP is clearly understood before wider stakeholders are invited to participate.

The key challenges the CoP wants to address is how to develop trust in the quality of the water, legal barriers to water reuse in Czech law, and creating awareness both at the local

and national level. Key stakeholders such as the Prague zoo and botanical garden would have to be approached through the municipality, and politicians are generally difficult to engage. No specific strategy for the latter had been defined, but a stepwise process with Professor Jiri Wanner, UCT, as a central resource person was foreseen.

Process since October 2020

By October 2020, a dialogue with Chancellor for Environment, City of Prague, was established, and a list of other stakeholders and introduction letters were written. There was also an online meeting where StormAqua participated, and both the CoP activity and practicalities concerning the demonstration were discussed. Creating awareness and trust, through the demonstration activity, and addressing the legal barrier was still considered as the main focus. Due to the new EU legislation on requirements for water reuse, a discussion has started, and Prof. Wanner is involved in the discussion with the two ministries. The National Czech Water Association was identified as another important stakeholder.

In November 2020, web pages for the Czech part of WIDER UPTAKE were created, and by January 2021 preparing for stakeholder interviews related to WP4 were considered as CoP activity. For the interviews, carried out in March, PVS was also involved, and while providing input for WP4, these interviews were also directly useful in relation to the CoP aims concerning trust and awareness-building. In May and June, PVS was also involved, in connection with the starting of experimental flower boxes.

A physical workshop was held on 29th June 2021. As presented below (Table 13) the workshop had broad and highly relevant stakeholder participation:

Table 13: Distribution of participants, Local CoP workshop in Prague 29th June 2021.

Institution / sector	No. of participants		
	In total	Male	Female
Ministry of Agriculture, Department of Agricultural Commodities	1		1
Ministry of the Environment, Department of Water Protection	1	1	
Research Institute for Soil and Water Conservation	3	2	1
Water Research Institute T. G. M.	3	2	1
CzWA - Czech Water Association	1	1	
Company ASIO TECH, spol. s r.o.	3	2	1
Journalists of “Our Water” - water information portal	2	1	1
UCT Prague, Department of Water Technology and Environmental engineering	5	3	2
CTU Prague	1	1	
PVS a.s.	1	1	
PVK a.s.	1	1	

The meeting included a visit to the demonstration site. Representatives of other stakeholders, i.e., the City of Prague and Water Utility Association of the Czech Republic “SOVAK” visited the demonstration units separately.

Figure 10: Prof. Wanner presenting in Prague, 29. June 2021. Photo: Iveta Ruzickova.

The topics covered during the workshop were a general introduction to the project, and presentations more specifically on the irrigation boxes, the WP2 database as well the results from the governance assessment carried out as part of WP4. Professor Wanner (Figure) presented the main goals as:

- 1) Demonstrating safe use of treated effluent for irrigation purposes in grey-green solutions for urban development with reasonable water transportation expenses.
- 2) Developing and applying monitoring and control schemes to adequately manage the health and quality risks associated with reuse of treated wastewater and recovered resources.
- 3) Optimization of the value chains to quantify the improved resource efficiency and economic benefits, also with respect to future applications.
- 4) Introduction of new legal categories of “reclaimed water” and “water reuse” into the Czech water law.

While the former two are technical tasks, the latter require multi-stakeholder engagement where the CoP is crucial.

On July 29th a meeting and excursion to the WWTP Brno within the project "Polygon of water recycling" took place, on the invitation of ASIO TECH, spol. s r. o. and with the Czech Water Association expert group “Purification and recycling of municipal wastewater. The meeting followed an exchange started at the 29th of June workshop. In addition to technical information, the main topic of discussion was how to improve legislation for water reuse in the Czech Republic.

On 1st September 2021 an external meeting of the Prague City Council Committee for the Environment on the premises of Prague Central WWTP followed by the excursion to the WIDER UPTAKE demonstration units. Then, on 6. October, the four core partners had a

combined meeting, discussing both technical matters and the stakeholder mapping requested for WP4.

Feedback and evaluation

While the Local CoP process was hindered by Covid-19 initially, it has picked up from June, and the Czech partners have also been very active to disseminate information about their demonstration in public and social media (reported under WP6). A summary evaluation of the interaction so far, provided by the facilitating research partner, is presented in Table 14.

Table 14: Summary evaluation of Local CoP activity in Prague, by facilitating research partner, month 18.

Criteria	Indicators	Reflections
Organizational support	Adequate planning and execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> very helpful sufficient support from all project partners
Atmosphere enabling stakeholder interaction and engagement	Nurturing existing relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> highly fruitful, especially relationships with both relevant ministries (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic, Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic), research institutions (T. G. Masaryk Water Research Institute, p. r. i., Research Institute for Soil and Water Conservation) and industrial partners (ASIO TECH, spol. s r.o.)
	Providing opportunity for new connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> establishing new efficient connections with the City of Prague and more intense involvement of media
	Conducive atmosphere	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> atmosphere supported fruitful discussion (despite pandemic regulations)
Representation and room for dialogue	Inclusion of all relevant perspectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> yes, different categories of stakeholders and project participants were involved
	Opportunity for participants to voice their opinions and concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> yes, everybody had a chance to express their own opinions and concerns
Convergence	Common conclusions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> common conclusions were supported by majority
	Change/expansion of own perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CoP activities help formulate our perspectives in more realistic ways
Identification of opportunities and challenges	Identification of joint actions, follow-ups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> external meeting of the Prague City Council Committee for the Environment on the premises of Prague Central WWTP followed by the excursion to Wider Uptake demonstration units

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> visits of Prague Deputy Mayor and Water Utility Association of the Czech Republic “SOVAK” to the demonstration units excursion to pilot plant units for water recycling at the WWTP Brno within the project "Polygon of water recycling" creation of very efficient communication tools among project participants
	Identification of actions, follow-ups in own organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> emphasis on dissemination and communication activities (presentation of the project to public, conferences, TV stations, newspapers)
Generation of knowledge	Increased knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> knowledge on the approach of politicians and public to water smartness
	Increased awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> awareness in the area of barriers (especially legislation and economic issues)

9.6 Local CoP, Netherlands

Virtual launching workshop

The initial meeting in the Amsterdam CoP was held on October 27th, 2020, as a two-hour virtual workshop, due to Covid-19. The aim of the meeting was to launch the Local CoP in the Amsterdam region and provide SINTEF, as Facilitating research partner, with more knowledge about the core processes and solutions in the Waternet/NPSP demo case. NTNU, as responsible for WP1 coordination, and TU Delft as local research partner, also participated, as shown below (Table 15).

Table 15: Participants at the initial (virtual) workshop for the Local CoP in the Netherlands.

Institution / sector	No. of participants		
	In total	Male	Female
Waternet	1	1	
NPSP	2	2	
TU Delft	4	3	1
NTNU	1	1	
SINTEF Community	2	1	1
SINTEF Digital	2	1	1

Waternet's main activities in WIDER UPTAKE are to supply raw materials from the water cycle for production of biocomposites, and in turn demonstrate the use of biocomposite products in a demo site. The price for the biocomposites will be higher than for conventional materials (for example when considering replacing tropical hardwood used for piers along canals), therefore marketing is crucial.

NPSP's goals in WIDER UPTAKE are to develop improved biocomposite materials and adapted production processes, systematically test and assess the new material, and optimize and (preferably) automate production. Furthermore, the aim is to verify the

characteristics of the new material and show how it can compete with traditional material. Currently, NPSP are developing demonstrators in order to prove the concept and qualities of the material in different settings. The goal of the local CoP is to demonstrate the sludge-based biocomposite material and promote its uptake, especially as a replacement for unsustainable tropical hardwood.

Among the barriers to upscaling are high costs and challenges related to getting the fibres (provided by Waternet) to specification, whereby they currently are transported to Germany and then returned to NPSP. There are also challenges related to public acceptance for products made from sludge, standards that are uncondusive for recycled materials, and conservative procurement practices. Addressing these issues requires dialogue and collaboration with multiple stakeholders, for which the CoP will be suitable.

Waternet is familiar with the CoP concept and has already established a CoP on biomass and biocomposites locally. This is still in early stage and has a focus on technical aspects, but there may well be synergies with the Local CoP in WIDER UPTAKE.

Further process

At the time of the launching workshop Waternet and NPSP planned to have regular WIDER UPTAKE work meetings, every 2 weeks. There was also the intention to meet regularly with TU Delft, approximately every other month. However, the demonstration case in the Netherlands has also been affected by Covid-19. The person who took over as main contact for WIDER UPTAKE suffered a relatively long period of sick leave in the spring and early summer of 2021, and the meetings have not been as regular as intended.

Currently the partners have a strong focus on the technical demonstration but are also making other efforts to promote the biocomposite material, e.g., the CoP manager has had meetings with various project managers in Waternet, and NPSP will have a stand displaying the material at a large trade fair in 2022. SINTEF has stayed in touch with the partners and got to know a set of wider stakeholders through interviews for the WP4 governance assessment, which was carried out in the first months of 2021. A virtual meeting with Peter van Gilst was held in September, and the next steps are to complete the stakeholder mapping and define a set of follow-up activities in WP4. Tentatively, there will be a physical meeting in the local CoP in Netherlands in January 2022, where also SINTEF will be present.

Feedback and evaluation

The feedback following the launching workshop was that it was friendly, with informative presentations and good discussions. However, most participants also pointed out that virtual meetings have their limitations, and that a physical meeting would have allowed deeper discussions and established CoP relations to a different extent. NPSP and Waternet have long-established relations and are collaborating well as core participants in the Local CoP. In relation to TU Delft, the focus has so far been on defining tasks and providing data for the PhD candidates. Looking forward, it will be important that all partners get a better overview of all the relevant activities that are going on locally, and inside WIDER UPTAKE, to be able to make use of synergies, and to make a plan for how to develop the CoP, both by pulling in more stakeholders and by utilising resources in the project WPs. A summary evaluation of the Local CoP activity so far, provided by the facilitating research partner, is presented in Table 16.

Table 16: Summary evaluation of Local CoP activity in the Netherlands by month 18, provided by the facilitating research partner.

Criteria	Indicators	Reflections
Organizational support	Adequate planning and execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not applicable
Atmosphere enabling stakeholder interaction and engagement	Nurturing existing relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Helpful in terms of further developing the relationship between NPSP and Waternet
	Providing opportunity for new connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Due to the pandemic, it has not been possible to arrange meetings with other stakeholders.
	Conducive atmosphere	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amicable (digital) atmosphere.
Representation and room for dialogue	Inclusion of all relevant perspectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only the core project partners, and academic partner were present (NPSP, Waternet, TU Delft and SINTEF)
	Opportunity for participants to voice their opinions and concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes, everybody had a chance to express their own opinions and concerns
Convergence	Common conclusions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The common conclusions agreed upon by the partners and had a shared vision in terms of what they want to achieve in WIDER UPTAKE
	Change/expansion of own perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unsure if the perspectives of the participants changed due to the meeting.
Identification of opportunities and challenges	Identification of joint actions, follow-ups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NPSP and Waternet to continue to communicate frequently
	Identification of actions, follow-ups in own organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continued work on a local CoP on biomass within Waternet. NPSP to involve new person when hired
Generation of knowledge	Increased knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There was no direct increase of knowledge on the behalf of the partners following the workshop on CoPs.
	Increased awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The partners seemed to be aware of the challenges faced in terms of the circular water solutions needed and what needed to be done.

9.7 Project CoP activities

As noted above, the kick-off workshop for WIDER UPTAKE, 18th June 2020, had to be virtual due to Covid-19. The virtual arrangement was smooth and surprisingly inspiring. It also provided a nice overview of the visions and plans for the project. However, it did not give room for the initial face-to-face relation-building at individual level that normally is part of

such an event. Many of the partners in WIDER UPTAKE did not have a pre-established history of collaboration or firm knowledge of the other partners' competence and topic areas. This has made it challenging to establish a CoP in a true sense, even though the PMT and the respective work packages are collaborating well.

While initiating the Local CoPs had most focus the first semester and the pandemic still hindered workshops gathering participants from multiple countries, T7.3 proposed and started planning for virtual workshops on selected cross-cutting topics in the first quarter of 2021.

By 9th June we were able to organize a workshop on struvite recovery. This was a two-hour event, with ample time for discussion and the following presentations:

- Alex Veltman, Waternet: 6 years of Phosphorus Recovery at WWTP Amsterdam West. Enhanced sewage sludge treatment with struvite recovery.
- Anders Øfsti/Morten Finborud, HIAS: From pilot to full-scale struvite recovery at HIAS.
- Mari Egeland and Anders Wold, IVAR: Bio-P and P- recovery at IVAR WWTP SNJ.

The idea was to include an external expert, while also providing room for the actors in WIDER UPTAKE to discuss their plans and experiences. Furthermore, it was reasoned that a focus on practice and practitioners would provide insights and impulses to most project participants, independently of disciplinary background. All persons on the WIDER UPTAKE contact list were invited, and attendance was good, with 53 participants representing the full spectre of cases and disciplines in WIDER UPTAKE. The feedback was very positive, thanks to good presentations and, we think, due to the practice focus and ample time for discussion.

7th October 2021, we had a similar event, on water reuse applied for agriculture. The agenda was as follows:

- Prof. Jiri Wanner (University of Chemistry and Technology Prague): Today's status on water reuse in Europe; barriers for wider uptake of water reuse; Where should we put our efforts?
- Dr. Pedro Simon (Sanitation and Wastewater Treatment Entity of the Region of Murcia, ESAMUR (Spain). Experiences on water reuse in the Murcia region within agriculture and tourism.
- Dr. Akon-Yamga (CSIR). Short update on status and future plans of the water reuse activities planned in the demonstration case in Ghana.
- Prof. Giorgio Mannina (UNIPA). Short update on status and future plans of the water reuse activities planned in the demonstration case in Ghana.

This time 57 persons attended, again from all the cases and institutes in the project. Since the presentations were many the meeting dragged out in time, but the feedback this time was also very good, suggesting that the project CoP activities meet a need and should be continued.

WP7 has also taken the initiative to a forum for "Young Professionals", which especially is targeting the PhD candidates, but also is open to others in the project.

Going forward, both these threads of activity will be continued. Biochar production and water reuse in urban settings, e.g., for blue-green infrastructure are some of the relevant topics, and more will be identified in the dialogue generated through the meetings.

Following the all-project 18-month meeting, to be held virtually 3-4 November, Task 7.3 will initiate a series of monthly 30-minute lunch webinars. Whether and how long this will continue will depend on attendance and level of interest from the broad group of project participants.

If the Covid-19 pandemic subsides as expected, we also hope to organize one "mobile lab" per semester, starting from 2022. However, some cross-cutting activities alone cannot establish a community. This is a challenge that the PMT, as well as WP leaders and case owners, also must relate actively to, as part of their project responsibilities.

9.8 Trans-project CoP activities

As noted above, the trans-project CoP involves experience-sharing and knowledge development with i) other projects under the Horizon2020 call "Water in the Context of the Circular Economy", ii) other relevant target groups, research communities and associations dealing with circular economy based on water resources.

So far, the former has been most in focus. Common meetings between the coordinators of the five projects financed under the mentioned call started in November 2020 and have been continued as quarterly meetings. The coordinators have prepared a common document outlining potential synergies and common topics in the projects. Based on this, working groups have been established on selected topics: stakeholder engagement, communication, and assessment methods.

Collaborating across the five "sister projects" and establishing a group with a separate name has been strongly encouraged by REA (previously EASME). The group has contributed input to public consultation on the urban wastewater treatment directive (UWWTD), It is also developing a position paper on "Shift from wastewater into Used Water concepts".

In addition, there have been meetings dedicated to specific topics, either for establishing working groups or meetings of the established working groups. The Working Group on Stakeholders is led by Stefania Munaretto (KWR), with Sigrid Damman (SINTEF) as the representative from WIDER UPTAKE. So far there has been three meetings, and the working group decided to focus on the following objectives:

- devise strategies to avoid stakeholder fatigue across the 5 projects;
- identify common topics across project's cases and define actions to exploit synergies (e.g., propose joint stakeholder meetings across the projects);
- identify lessons learned from SHs engagement across the 5 projects to report as joint recommendations/lesson learned report to the EC at the end of the projects
- others to be defined if needed

A Teams site, hosted by TU Delft, has been established for the coordinator group. The communication teams of the "sister projects" have also exchanged coordinates for website and social media to ensure that the target audiences know about all the projects in this

trans-project CoP. Furthermore, ULTIMATE, and WIDER UPTAKE have initiated dialogue about potential common activities for the Young Professionals.

In the coming period, building relations with other relevant research communities and institutions in the EU and beyond will also be prioritised.

10 Lessons learned and way forward

In line with this design, there are ongoing CoP activities and positive feedback from participants, both at the local- and project CoP level. At the trans-project level, a structure for collaboration between the five "sister projects" has been established, which is likely to increase cross-learning and strengthen the impact of the project at EU level.

The Local CoPs have so far taken slightly different approaches. In Norway and the Netherlands, the initial approach has been "bottom-up", starting with case partners and industry stakeholders. In Italy, the Czech Republic and Ghana, the focus has been more on public stakeholders, engaging with the relevant city authorities and public agencies. This seems appropriate considering the barriers and opportunities identified for the respective solutions, as well as the stated visions for the local CoPs.

What is most fruitful and desirable in terms of meeting formats and interaction to achieve the local visions and aims, is also variable and influenced by cultural factors. For example, starting the meeting with a prayer and appointing a Chairman to run the workshop with a certain eloquence and degree of formality may be appropriate in the Ghanaian context, whereas a more informal style may work better in Norway. Both come with their own advantages and challenges as regards participation, voice, and community development. Likewise, policy dialogue in Sicily and the Czech Republic may require different approaches.

Still, with a view to IS development and the planned inputs to and outputs from the project WPs, all the Local CoPs should aim to follow the four-step process discussed above (section 6.2), gradually engaging broader set of stakeholders.

Whereas some Local CoPs are making more active use of the project and associated resources, e.g., in Sicily and the Czech Republic WIDER UPTAKE websites in local language are established and the project is employed actively as the frame for meetings and other activities, others have so far worked more on their own and distinguished less between efforts in WIDER UPTAKE and their regular activities. While the latter carries a potential for fragmentation, the variety of approaches also involves a potential for learning across the cases, about different strategies, and ways of working to achieve wider uptake of the project solutions.

The different Local CoPs have also got different experience and expertise, e.g., NPSP and Grønn Vekst have extensive experience from developing and marketing circular products, whereas Sicily has law experts, professor Wanner in the Czech case is closely involved in policy dialogue at EU level, Ghana has experts in science and technology policy research and the team from SINTEF includes expertise in innovation and transition management. Again, there is a huge potential for cross-learning and co-development, that may be exploited more as the project progresses and relations can develop through face-to-face as well as virtual meetings.

Considering the Project CoP, the need for physical meetings cannot be over-emphasized. As soon as it is possible without violating national rules and recommendations concerning Covid-19, key partners and if feasible the whole consortium should meet. The planned virtual interactions will anyway be facilitated to maintain relations in between and beyond face-to-face encounters.

When it comes to trans-project CoP activity, a good basis has been put in place through the formalised collaboration between the "sister projects". This will be all the more important as the project enters a phase when more outcomes are produced and more dialogue is needed to validate, disseminate, and implement results. In the coming period, other relevant communities, both within and beyond the EU, will also be addressed. Furthermore, it is important that the dialogue extends beyond the respective coordinators and project management teams, to include experience-sharing across cases and research groups working on related topics.

11 Conclusion

This report has provided an overview of the CoP design applied in WIDER UPTAKE. The work on CoPs has thus far centred on the demonstration cases, where *local CoPs* have been established to facilitate collaboration and engagement with relevant stakeholders in the project participating countries. Despite Covid-19, all CoPs are active and progressing towards their stated aims. At the *project CoP* level, virtual workshops on cross-cutting topics and a forum for "Young Professionals" have been initiated, but face-face interaction and further efforts from the PMT are needed. At the *trans-project CoP* level, a collaboration has been established with the other projects funded under the call "Water in the Context of the Circular Economy". While this is crucial to enable wider uptake of the project solutions, other relevant communities, both within and beyond the EU, will also be addressed in the coming phase. To reach further towards realising the aims of the CoPs established thus far, there is a need for more face-to-face interaction, both between the partners in WIDER UPTAKE, and with stakeholders outside the project.

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Annex 1: 2-pager on CoPs in WIDER UPTAKE

Communities of Practice (CoP) in WIDER UPTAKE

What?

Communities of Practice (CoP) is a way to organize learning and knowledge development between a range of stakeholders who share an interest in a particular topic or have a common goal. While some CoP develop naturally, others are purposely designed. An example of a CoP could be engineers working on deep-sea drilling. When CoP is applied as a learning concept, the ambition is to enhance the pre-existing knowledge and practices of those involved. This is done through experience-sharing, relation-building and joint efforts to develop new knowledge in the interface between different practices and disciplines. So, why is this important in the context of Wider Uptake?

Why?

There are several reasons why we believe that developing CoPs in Wider Uptake is a good idea. First of all, it is a way of coordinating efforts in order to succeed with the implementation of the different solutions in the demo cases. By setting up CoPs and getting stakeholders involved from an early stage, we can develop a joint understanding of what our common goal(s) are, and how we can reach them.

Secondly, the CoPs will enable interaction between the different stakeholders involved in the demo cases, both industrial actors, local interest organizations, municipality representatives and others.

As such, the *Local CoPs* will provide a forum for learning between different local actors. The aim is also that the different demo cases can learn from each other. This will be facilitated by so-called *Project CoPs*, where the different members, across country boundaries, can share and co-develop further knowledge on particular technologies or products (e.g., fertilizers), business concepts and policy recommendations.

The three CoP levels.

In addition to contributing to the successful implementation of the solutions in the different demo cases, the CoPs are essential to increase the knowledge and awareness of the wider impact of these solutions. The overall aim in Wider Uptake is to enhance the exploitation rate of natural water resources. Key to this is achieving industrial symbiosis, e.g., water reuse and resource recovery. A better understanding of what this requires and entails, in terms of stakeholder collaboration and business model development, is critical to our success. It may also inspire those involved in the CoPs to pursue circular economy in other domains. This way, the CoPs can have a broader impact on sustainability transition. So, how will we go about it?

How?

Each *Local CoP* will be led by a Local CoP Manager, from the utility or research partner 'owning' the demo case. Beside technology demonstration, each case has as an objective to facilitate wider uptake of the water-smart solutions. The specific challenge and approach vary from case to case. The case owner and local partners are in charge of the process but will be supported by the project CoP team to apply Communities of Practice as a framework for cross-sector learning and co-development. Instead of the occasional workshop and dissemination at the end, we will define a series of workshops that meet both case and work package needs, while engaging with key stakeholders to achieve the project objectives. The specific number, timing and format of workshops may vary, but the process will have four basic steps:

Four steps in Local CoP development.

The CoP Managers will be responsible for arranging local workshops that are relevant for their cases. The project CoP team will be available for guidance and discussion on how workshops can be organized and how different aspects of innovation management can be addressed. It is, however, essential that the local case owners and stakeholders set the agenda. *Project CoPs* will be organized and led by key researchers and the project management team. The CoP concept will also frame the project's efforts to build knowledge and engage with stakeholders at a trans-project level.

A working document with more detailed information on the CoP concept and its application is found on the project site in Teams. A calendar to coordinate CoP development and other project activities is also available, and a resource base on relevant moderation tools and techniques will be provided by month 6. A CoP workshop report template has been made. It is important that this template is used systematically, to document the process and facilitate learning across the cases. To ensure that the CoPs contribute to co-learning and knowledge development for all parties involved, workshop participants will be asked to fill evaluation forms at the end of each workshop. These will provide key insights into how different stakeholders experience being part of the CoPs and the Wider Uptake project. In turn, these insights can be used by the CoP team to help adjust the content and form of future workshops or confirm that the CoPs are on track.

In terms of project deliverables, the monitoring and results of the CoP activities will be documented in D7.6 and D7.8, Reports on Communities of Practice in month 18 and 44. The CoPs will provide important input to all work packages but be particularly important for the work on business models and transition pathways in WP4 and the final roadmapping and policy recommendations from WP6.

Annex 2: Evaluation form, Local CoP workshops

Evaluation Form (WIDER UPTAKE CoP MEETINGS)

Place: _____ Date: _____

It was a pleasure to have you in this meeting. We would like to know your opinion, so that we can improve future events and meet your expectations. Thank you for your collaboration!

Name (optional): _____

Organization (optional): _____

Which type of stakeholder do you represent?

Private sector	Public agency/organization	Politician	Academia	Other (specify):

What is your motivation for participating in this meeting (e.g., learning, ensure stakeholder perspectives, business development, networking, environmental concern etc.)?

<p>List your motivation(s):</p>
--

Please rate the extent to which you agree with each of the following statements:
(1=strongly disagree; 2=disagree 3=neutral; 4=agree; 5=strongly agree; N.A=not applicable)

1. Meeting logistics and stakeholder engagement	
1.1 I received the information about the meeting and materials well in advance	
1.2 The presentations and speakers were clear and understandable	
1.3 I already knew the people present at the meeting	
1.4 During the meeting I improved or made new connections for my professional network	
1.5 I believe others were communicating openly with me	
1.6 The way the discussion was facilitated and moderated supported the meeting objectives	
Comments: (optional)	

2. Awareness and increased understanding	
2.1 I believe that a sufficiently broad range of stakeholders was invited*	

*List stakeholders you would have liked to see attending the meeting (<i>optional</i>)	
2.2 I actively welcomed new members of the community	
2.3 I had sufficient opportunities to provide input to the discussion	
2.4 The atmosphere during the meeting was friendly and respectful	
2.5 Differences and (potential) conflicts among us were addressed in a constructive manner	
2.6 I gained a better understanding of the perspective of the stakeholders involved (e.g., water utility, public agencies, researchers, farmers etc.)	
2.7 I believe the different stakeholders have a shared vision of what we want to achieve	
Comments: (<i>optional</i>)	

3. Outcomes and conclusions	
3.1 There was enough time to reflect on our collective experience and functioning as a group	
3.2 I have a better understanding of the language/terminology used by the participants outside my organization/work package	
3.3 Participating in the meeting increased my knowledge on the topic of the meeting	
3.4 I am aware of my own role in the project and how each of us can contribute to the project goals	
3.5 I believe that clear conclusions were formulated at the end of the meeting	
3.6 I believe the actions formulated can promote water-smart solutions	
3.7 After participating in the meeting, I identified (potential) improvement efforts for my organization/ work package	
3.8 My expectations on the outcomes of the meeting were met	
Comments: (<i>optional</i>)	

Pros and cons of the local CoP
In your opinion, what were the <u>most positive</u> and <u>less positive</u> aspects of the meeting?
<u>Most positive:</u>
<u>Less positive:</u>

Suggestions for improvement
What suggestions for improvement do you have for future meetings?

Thank you!

Please give this questionnaire back to the workshop organizer before leaving.